

DEPUTY ETIQUETTE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF A LOCAL COUNCIL DEPUTY

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Annotation. In this article, the activities of deputies of the local council in the legislation of Uzbekistan, their concept of deputy etiquette, the procedure for the implementation of deputy etiquette, the requirements and conditions of deputy etiquette, the consequences of following and not following the etiquette of deputies, the ability of a deputy to establish relations with the public, the local council among the members of the parliament, they discussed the importance of cooperation and team work and other such aspects. Also, based on the comparative analysis of deputy ethics, relevant conclusions and suggestions are made.

Key words: deputy, etiquette, deputy etiquette, local council, district, public trust, loyalty, quality service, public event, social sphere, personal ethics, constructive, teamwork, decision making.

Local council deputies play an important role in the social, economic and political life of society. Their activities include expressing the interests of the local population, solving problems in society, and ensuring the participation of the population in the decision-making process. For each member of society, deputies should feel a great responsibility to understand and solve problems in their districts, to create effective mechanisms to take into account the needs of the population.

Therefore, parliamentary etiquette is very important. Deputies' etiquette is a complex of ethical, moral and social norms that must be followed in the activities of deputies. It manifests itself in areas such as public relations, decision-making process, accountability and responsibility. Deputies must adhere to decency and ethical standards in order to gain the trust of the public, take their opinions into account, make responsible decisions and ensure social justice.

When local councilors communicate with the public, they influence the public not only by their work, but also by their personal ethics, manners and morals. Every action, word, creative initiative and proposal of the deputies can shape or change the trust in them among the public. Therefore, the manners of

deputies are the main factor in serving the public, feeling social responsibility and implementing democratic principles .

A deputy's personal behavior is the main factor in influencing the public. Deputies should be an example to the public in their work, gain their attention and trust. For example, a deputy should actively participate in public meetings, local events, be sincere and constructive in communication with the population. Such relations increase the reputation of the deputy and increase the interest of the public. It is important for MPs to support the public with their personal rules and flexibility to ensure effectiveness in addressing public concerns .

A deputy's ability to communicate with the public is one of the important conditions for his effective work. Deputies should understand the problems of the population and try to solve their needs. Opinions, proposals and involvement of the population play a key role in the effective performance of the deputy's work. Deputies should be actively involved in effective communication with the public, determining the needs of the population and protecting their interests. Participation in public events and open dialogues helps to strengthen the relationship of the deputy with the public. Deputies should also use modern technologies and social networks to actively communicate with the public.

Decisions made by deputies must be clear and transparent to the public. A sense of responsibility, decency and transparency in the decision-making process increases public trust. Deputies should conduct their activities openly and clearly to the public. If deputies make their decisions in a closed, non-transparent manner, they may lose the public's trust in them. Therefore, deputies should work in cooperation with the public and take their opinions into account. Transparency of decisions strengthens trust between deputies and the public, which increases the effectiveness of democratic processes .

Deputies should be open to criticism in their activities. In such cases, it is possible to have a constructive dialogue and correct the original picture. Kritika helps the professional growth of the MP and increases public trust. Deputies should accept criticism as a tool to improve their work. Their constructive relations, active adaptation to changes based on suggestions and requests will benefit the society. Mutually constructive miracles among deputies, suggestions aimed at improving each other's work are also the basis of successful work .

Cooperation and teamwork among local councilors is a key success factor. Establishing constructive communication between deputies and doing their work together increases the public's trust in them. Working together for common goals, the feeling of responsibility of each deputy, will lead to positive

results in the society. In this, the cooperation of deputies, mutual trust, cooperation, and openness to suggestions will help to implement a successful social policy .

It is very important to conduct continuous education and training to improve the professional level and ethical standards of MPs. It helps to identify problems in the work of deputies, find solutions for them and strengthen relations with the public. Seminars and workshops organized for deputies serve to provide the necessary knowledge and skills to establish effective communication with the public, conduct constructive dialogue, and strengthen cooperation. Such trainings help MPs learn not only the basics of legislation, but also social media, marketing and public relations development.

MPs should work to serve the public. They should constantly communicate with the public, striving to provide quality service to the population, quickly and effectively solve the problems of the population. In this case, the deputy's consideration of the opinions received from the public is important in achieving positive changes. Public services, learning effective mechanisms for solving population problems, development of local economy should be one of the main goals for deputies.

In conclusion, we can say that in the work of a deputy of the local council, the etiquette of the deputy is not only ethical standards, but also a means of serving the society and gaining the trust of the population. Deputies should remember to maintain decency and establish cordial relations with the public while performing their duties. This, in turn, serves to increase the efficiency of the state and the sustainable development of society.

Deputies' etiquette undoubtedly plays an important role in strengthening social relations and protecting the interests of the population in a democratic society. Deputies, together with the people, should conduct their activities with decency and responsibility in order to achieve success. In addition, in order to increase public confidence in deputies, it is important to maintain high ethical standards in their activities, establish communication with the public, and ensure the transparency of every decision.

The manners of a deputy determine not only the personal creativity of the deputy, but also the general development of the society. It, in turn, is one of the important sources for ensuring effective development of society in the political, economic and social spheres. Deputies should pursue their own goals in society and always take into account the interests of the people, which, in turn, will shape effective and constructive democratic processes.

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